

Using Signal-detection Theory to Enhance IRT Methods: A Clinical Judgment Example

Signal-Detection Theory

SCORING MODEL

Multiple Response Highlight

The nurse is assessing a 52-year-old male client with esophageal cancer who is receiving continuous enteral nutrition at 63 mL/h via a percutaneous gastrostomy tube.

The nurse notes the following:

Time: 0730

Vital signs:

blood pressure	98/72
heart rate	112
respirations	18
oxygen saturation	98% on room air
temperature	98.9° F (37.2° C)

Throat pain rated 2 on a scale of 0 (no pain) to 10 (severe pain)

Abdomen soft

Bowel sounds active x 4

Dry mucous membranes of mouth

Urine output 100 mL over the past 4 hours

Laboratory test results:

serum potassium	3.8 mEq/L (3.8 mmol/L)
serum sodium	147 mEq/L (147 mmol/L)
blood urea nitrogen	24 mg/dL (8.6 mmol/L)
hematocrit	50% (0.50)

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Multiple Response Highlight: Examinee 2

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Multiple Response Highlight: Examinee 3

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Dry mucous membranes of mouth

Urine output 100 mL over the past 4 hours

Laboratory test results:

serum potassium	3.8 mEq/L (3.8 mmol/L)
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Scoring multiple response item types

- Dichotomous scoring
 - All or none
 - Might not be suitable as item complexity increases
- Corrected scoring
 - Subtract incorrect from correct

Number of Cues Recognized

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Multiple response item types

- Two component processes underlying responding behavior
 - A latent trait underlies sensitivity to relevant information
 - A latent trait underlies endorsement bias

Signal-Detection Model

- Theoretical framework evaluate choice/decision making (Green & Swet, 1966; Luce, 1959; Tversky, 1972)
- Recognize relevant from irrelevant cues
 - Keyed answers are relevant (+) and non-keyed are irrelevant (-), allows for detection of FP and FN responding

Scoring multiple response item types

- Signal-detection theory

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Scoring multiple response item types

- Signal-detection theory (DeCarlo, 1998; 2010; 2011; 2012)

$$P(y = 1|S) = \Phi((\Psi_S - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|N) = \Phi((\Psi_N - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi(-c + dX)$$

$$P(y_{ij} = 1|c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi\left(-c_i + d_i\mathbf{X} - (-\alpha_j + \delta_j\mathbf{X})\right)$$

True/False Scoring

- Potentially flexible model
 - Combines principals of testlet model (Wainer & Kelly, 1987) with SDT concept
- Scoring rule:
 - All response options are nested in a common stimulus
 - Each response option is treated as a unique 'cue'
 - Scored as T/F (+/-) or Relevant/Irrelevant
- Potentially useful when non-endorsement is as important as endorsement
 - Ex. cue recognition, evaluating outcomes, taking action, etc.

	Endorse	Ignore
Valid	1	0
Invalid	0	1

Subset Model

- Scoring rule:
 - Only subsets of the correct answer key set are considered partially correct
 - Any endorsement of incorrect option results in Score = 0
- Potentially useful when partial knowledge/skill should be rewarded
- Allows for assigning multiple score categories to an item

Empirical Example: Methods

- Participants (N = 9,132) answered from 4 to 8 items
 - Randomly seeded into exam
- MR Items = 139
 - Between 400 and 600 responses per item
 - Stems: “Choose ALL that apply ...”
- Evaluate items with a number of scoring approaches
 - Rasch model (base)
 - Partial Credit Model (PCM; Masters, 1982) for (1) T/F ; (2) Subset models
 - SDT
- Evaluate the utility of parameters for providing useful feedback to SME/CDs

Results

	Item_Dif_TrueFalse	Item_Dif_SubSet	Item_Dif_SDT	Item_Bias_SDT
Item_Dif_Rasch	.852	.893	-.871	.265
Item_Dif_TrueFalse		.804	-.890	.289
Item_Dif_SubSet			-.808	.543
Item_Dif_SDT				-.162

True/False Partial Credit Model

Subset Partial Credit Model

Some Visualizations: Interesting Cases

- Normal Example
- NOTE: only response sets with > 20 responses are shown

- High 'c' item: notice the under endorsement
- Normal looking item
 - {1, 3} common subset
 - {2, 5} little more difficult to endorse

- Low 'c' item: notice the over endorsement
- 2 large, high-ability groups also endorsed '4'
- Are '3' and '4' potentially correct or even 'not incorrect'

- A large, high-ability group also endorsed '3'
- Also, all groups with higher average theta endorsed '3'
- Is '3' a potentially correct answer or just a very sweet distractor?

- Example where subsets of similar cardinality could have differences in ability
- $\{1, 3\}$ NE $\{1, 5\}$ or $\{3, 5\}$

Conclusions

- Different models can map to distinct cognitive processes
- All models appear to be very similar w.r.t. difficulty
 - IRT models provide a structure for category scaling
 - SDT provides information on responding bias – not highly correlated with difficulty
 - SDT can isolate recognition errors, sensitivity vs. bias
- Useful approaches to provide item level feedback to SME/CDs
- Possible future investigations:
 - Using the SDT model for individuals – profile of individual bias

QUESTIONS?

THANK YOU!